

PHYSICOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF BOREHOLE WATER IN GAJIRAM: SAFETY AND SUITABILITY FOR HOME USE

Ibrahim Musa Abdullahi

Department of Environmental Science, University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria

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Abstract: This study assessed the quality of borehole water used for domestic purposes in three selected wards—Ajari, Kumburi, and Gajiram 2 Primary School—in Gajiram, Nganzai Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria. Water samples were collected over a six-month period (January, February, March, June, July, and August 2019) and analyzed using standard procedures for various physicochemical parameters including temperature, pH, turbidity, electrical conductivity, anions (sulphate, phosphate, nitrate, and chloride), cations (Ca^{2+} , Na^+ , Mg^{2+}), and heavy metals (As, Cr, Fe, Mn, Pb, Zn, Cd, and Co).

The results revealed that temperature and turbidity levels in all three boreholes exceeded the permissible limits set by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA). The pH, electrical conductivity, and most heavy metal concentrations were within acceptable limits, except for manganese during the dry season. Sulphate recorded the highest concentration among the anions, while phosphate was undetectable in Ajari. Sodium was the most prevalent cation, whereas magnesium showed the lowest concentration. Iron was the most abundant heavy metal across all sites, with notable spatial variation in its distribution.

Despite seasonal variations, statistical analysis indicated no significant differences in water quality parameters between the dry and wet seasons. The findings suggest that, although some parameters exceed recommended thresholds, the overall groundwater quality in Gajiram remains within acceptable ranges for most domestic uses. However, consistent monitoring and community health sensitization are recommended due to the potential health risks from elevated turbidity and temperature, and the occasional presence of heavy metals.

Keywords: Borehole Water, Heavy Metals, Gajiram, Groundwater Quality, Borno State

Introduction

Access to clean and safe drinking water is a fundamental human necessity and a major determinant of public health. In many developing countries, including Nigeria, groundwater sources such as boreholes and hand-dug wells provide the

primary source of domestic water supply, especially in rural areas. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2006), more than 1.1 billion people globally lack access to improved drinking water sources. In the Nigerian context, the lack of basic water infrastructure, compounded by a growing

population, unregulated agricultural practices, industrial discharges, and inadequate waste disposal systems, has rendered the quality of available groundwater a subject of growing concern (Efe, 2005).

In the northeastern region of Nigeria, and particularly in Borno State, the dependence on borehole water is heightened due to the arid climate, poor surface water resources, and limited government-managed water supply infrastructure. Gajiram, a rapidly developing area within Nganzai Local Government Area (LGA) of Borno State, exemplifies the challenges faced by rural populations in accessing quality water. Poor sanitation habits, insufficient regulatory oversight, and increasing anthropogenic activities have been implicated in the contamination of these water sources. Groundwater quality here is significantly influenced by environmental conditions, the hydrogeological properties of the area, and human activities such as open defecation, agricultural runoff, and improper waste disposal.

Groundwater pollution is a major environmental concern due to its latent effects and the difficulty in remedying contamination once it occurs. Unlike surface water, which may be more immediately impacted and visibly degraded, polluted groundwater may continue to pose risks long after the original source of contamination has ceased. The quality of groundwater is determined by various physical, chemical, and biological parameters, including temperature, pH, turbidity, electrical conductivity, and concentrations of anions, cations, and trace heavy metals. These parameters not only determine water

safety for human consumption but also affect its suitability for domestic and agricultural uses.

In Gajiram and surrounding areas, boreholes are often located close to potential sources of contamination, including pit latrines, soakaways, animal pens, and refuse dumps. This spatial proximity heightens the risk of leachate infiltration and pollutant migration into aquifers, especially during the rainy season when water percolation rates are high. Studies such as those by Ukpong et al. (2015) have noted that the rapid proliferation of unregulated boreholes in Nigerian rural areas often ignores hydrogeological surveys and environmental safety guidelines, increasing the vulnerability of these water sources to contamination. Furthermore, agricultural practices in and around Nganzai LGA also contribute significantly to groundwater contamination. The use of fertilizers, herbicides, and pesticides introduces nitrates, phosphates, and potentially hazardous organic compounds into the soil, some of which leach into the groundwater system. Joarder et al. (2008) noted that even in countries with relatively lower agricultural chemical use, pollution of groundwater from these sources remains a critical issue. Feedlots and poultry farms are common in the region and can introduce high levels of nutrients, pathogens, and organic pollutants into nearby water systems.

Heavy metals such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), arsenic (As), iron (Fe), and manganese (Mn) are of particular concern due to their toxicity, persistence in the environment, and bioaccumulative properties. Even at low concentrations, these metals can have deleterious effects on human health, ranging from neurological

damage to kidney failure and various forms of cancer. The WHO and NESREA have set permissible limits for these elements in drinking water to safeguard public health. However, research suggests that in many rural areas of Nigeria, these standards are often exceeded, particularly during dry seasons when dilution effects are reduced.

Several studies conducted in other regions have reported alarming levels of water contamination. Prakash and Somashekar (2006), for instance, analyzed over 1000 borehole and hand-pump samples in India and found that over 80% were unsuitable for domestic use due to elevated iron concentrations and microbial contamination. Similarly, Jameel et al. (2006) and Mor et al. (2009) identified effluent discharge, agricultural runoff, and domestic sewage as primary sources of groundwater contamination in their respective studies.

Given these concerns, assessing the groundwater quality in Gajiram is not only timely but essential. Such an assessment provides critical data that inform water safety interventions, public health planning, and resource management. It also aligns with Sustainable Development Goal 6, which aims to ensure the availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all. The present study, therefore, seeks to evaluate the physicochemical and heavy metal parameters of borehole water from three selected wards in Gajiram—Ajari, Kumburi, and Gajiram 2 Primary School—across both dry and rainy seasons. The objective is to determine compliance with WHO and NESREA drinking water standards and to explore the seasonal variation in water quality parameters.

Understanding the quality of borehole water is crucial for developing effective mitigation strategies to improve water safety. This includes promoting water treatment, enhancing community awareness, instituting stricter regulations on borehole drilling and placement, and integrating water quality monitoring into routine public health activities. It is hoped that this study will serve as a baseline for further groundwater quality investigations in the region and ultimately contribute to safeguarding the health of Gajiram's residents.

Material and Methods

The Study Area

Nganzai is a local government area in Borno State, Nigeria. Nganzai is located in the northern senatorial district of Borno

State. It lies on the coordinates of Latitude 12.2910N and Longitude 13.1233E. It has an area of about

2467km and a population of 99799 census 2006. The raining season's starts from April to November. Rainfall is between 1500mm – 2000mm with July – September as the wettest months and December as the driest. Nganzai has temperature of moderately high throughout the year with a low range. The mean

annual maximum and minimum temperature are 47°C and 25°C respectively

Map 1: Map of Borno state showing the study sites

map 2: Map the study points

Sample collection

Three (3) boreholes were selected at different locations of the study area. The water samples were collected from the sampling points in pre-cleaned plastic containers and labelled appropriately. The collected borehole water samples were aseptically transferred into sterile containers and brought to chemistry research laboratory, Yobe State University Damaturu for preparation and analysis.

Sample Preparation and Sample

Analysis

One hundred millilitres (100 ml) of the water sample was measured and the pH was determined using Ecotests pH meter at the site. The temperature was determined using thermometer, while conductivity was determined using conductivity meter. The turbidity of the wastewater and surface water were determined using the absorbimetric method of the spectrophotometer. The stored programme of the spectrophotometer was calibrated using the standard for formazin solution as a reference. Nitrate, sulphates, phosphates and chlorides, Calcium, Sodium and Magnesium were determined using DR/2010 HACH portable data logging spectrophotometer.

The samples were digested according to the method described by Clesceri et al., (1989). Standard Solutions of each element were prepared according to manufacturer procedure for Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy used. The concentrations of the standards were within anticipated range of the

unknown sample. Absorbances of these standards were measured at the maximum wavelength of the analytes. A plot of the absorbance against the standard concentration gives a straight line graph passing through the origin according to

Bear's law is ob The digested samples were used to determine the concentration of the heavy metals using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Buck scientific model 210GP). Absorbances of these samples were measured at their specific wavelengths. From the standard calibration curve (Beer Lambert's law), absorbances of the unknown were measured at their specific wavelength of their absorption and read out from the graph.

Data collected were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to assess whether heavy metals varied significantly between dry and rainy season samples. Probability less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) were considered statistically significant. All statistical calculations were performed using graph pad instant (2003) for windows. Results were presented in mean \pm standard deviation.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 present the mean values of some physical parameters of groundwater samples of Gajiram, Nganzai local government area of Borno state. The results revealed that the highest and lowest mean pH in dry season is 6.89 ± 0.19 and 6.82 ± 0.18 while in rainy season were 6.90 ± 0.03 and 5.74 ± 1.09 respectively. The pH in all study areas fall below the WHO (7.0-8.5) recommended limit. Discharge of untraveled effluence with such a pH into

ponds rivers or on lands for any purpose may be detrimental to soil fauna and aquatic biota such as zooplankton and fishes, since low pH level may affect the physiology of fish (Islam et al., 2014). The mean concentration of turbidity revealed that the highest and lowest mean in dry season are 41.36 ± 20.37 and 3.59 ± 1.95 respectively while in rainy season, were 3.59 ± 1.95 and 10.45 ± 0.56 respectively. The turbidity observed in was above the recommended limits of WHO (5 – 25 NTU) while the other samples in B1, B2 and B3 were within and below limit. The results were found statistically significant difference ($P < 0.05$) among the borehole not the season. Water turbidity is very important because high turbidity is often associated with higher level of disease causing microorganism, such as bacteria and other parasites (Shittu et al., 2008).

The mean electrical conductivity level observed in the study area revealed that the highest and lowest mean in dry season were 8.68 ± 7.01 and 7.72 ± 4.86 respectively while in rainy season were 63.42 ± 12.38 and 33.80 ± 13.16 respectively. The electrical conductivity observed in all the samples in both dry

and raining season were found below the standard limit of WHO 2011 ($400 \mu\text{cm}$). The statistical analysis revealed that there was no significant difference between the seasons. Although there is disease or disorder associated with conductivity of drinking water (NSDWQ 2007) electrical conductivity is a measure of water's capacity to convey an electric current. This property is related to the total concentration of dissolved substances in the water. The more dissolved salt in water, the stronger is current in flow and higher the electrical conductivity in short EC of water increases with salt.

The mean temperature observed in the study area revealed that the highest and lowest mean in dry season were 42.77 ± 0.46 and 33.80 ± 13.16 respectively while in rainy season were 42.1 ± 0 and 40.2 ± 0 respectively. The mean temperature observed in all the samples in both dry and raining season were found above the standard limit of WHO (35°C). The result was not found statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) among the boreholes and also between the seasons. This may be due to the seasonal variation at the time of sample collection.

Table 1: mean concentration of some physical parameters in groundwater of Gajiram location for dry and raining season (2019)

Location	pH		Turbidity (Ntu)		Conductivity (μCm)		Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	
	DRY	WET	DRY	WET	DRY	WET	DRY	WET
B1	6.82 ± 0.18		41.36 ± 20.37		7.72 ± 4.86		41.67 ± 1.85	
		6.85 ± 0.03		5.89 ± 0.31		63.42 ± 12.38		40.2 ± 0
B2	6.86 ± 0.27		3.59 ± 1.95		8.68 ± 7.01		42.77 ± 0.46	
		5.74 ± 1.09		0.40 ± 0.17		33.80 ± 13.16		41.73 ± 0.12
B3	6.89 ± 0.19		9.23 ± 1.30		8.35 ± 6.79		42.53 ± 0.23	
		6.90 ± 0.03		4.63 ± 0.25		57.73 ± 1.35		42.1 ± 0

WHO 7.0-8.5 5-25NTU 400µ/cm 35°C

Key: B1- Ajari Borehole, B2- Kumburi Borehole, B3 –Gajiram 2 Primary School Borehole

Table 2: Mean concentration of some heavy parameters in groundwater of gajiram location for dry seasons (January, February and March 2019)

Location	Parameters for Dry Season (mg/L)							
	C	Cd	Para Fe	Cr	Pb	As	Zn	Mn
B1	N	0.002±0.0	0.395±0.1	0.005±0.0	0.006±0.0	ND	0.291±0.3	0.065±0.0
	D	01	92	13	07		60	53
B2	N	ND	0.114±0.0	ND	0.006±0.0	ND	0.352±0.5	0.062±0.0
	D		78		04		18	19
B3	N	ND	0.068±0.0	ND	0.006±0.0	ND	0.292±0.3	0.058±0.0
	D		24		05		81	32
WHO	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.05	0.05	0.1	5	0.02

Key: B1- Ajari Borehole, B2- kumburi Borehole, B3 –Gajiram 2 Primary School Borehole, ND: Not detected

Table 3: mean concentration of some heavy metal parameters in groundwater of gajiram location for raining season (June, July and August 2019)

Location	Parameters for Raining Season (mg/L)							
	CO	Cd	Fe	Cr	Pb	As	Zn	Mn
B1	ND	ND	0.470±0.0	0.001±0.0	0.006±0.0	ND	0.002±0.0	0.001±0.0
			41	01	01		03	001
B2	ND	ND	0.050±0.0	ND	0.004±0.0	ND	ND	ND
			52		02			
B3	ND	ND	0.077±0.0	ND	0.006±0.0	ND	ND	ND
			67		01			
WHO	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.05	0.05	0.1	5	0.02

Key: B1- Ajari Borehole, B2- Kumburi Borehole, B3 –Gajiram 2 Primary School Borehole,

ND: Not Detected

Figure 1, 2 and 3 present concentrations of Anions and cations in different parts of gajiram groundwater samples for Dry season from Nganzai local

government area, Borno state. In the sample analysed Sulphate has highest concentration in January and February 2019 while Chloride was high in March 2019. The concentration of Sulphate was high with

68.57mg/l and Chloride was high 83.18 mg/l. Phosphate showed least concentration of 0mg/l. The other of Anions and cations in the sample were $SO_4 > Na > Cl > NO_3 > Ca > Mg > F > PO_4$ in January and February while $Cl > SO_4 > Na > Ca > NO_3 > F > Mg > F > PO_4$ in March. Figure 4, 5 and 6 present concentrations of Anions and cations in different parts of Gajiram groundwater samples for raining season from Nganzai local government area, Borno state. In the sample analyzed Chloride has highest concentration. The concentration of Chloride was high with 8.82 mg/l. Phosphate and Fluoride showed least concentration of 0mg/l. The other of physical parameters in the sample were $Cl > SO_4 > Mg > Na > NO_3 > Ca > F > PO_4$.

The high sulphate concentration detected in the effluents are also known to cause eutrophication and algal boom, (ogiehor et al., 2000) these sulphates can be precipitated by calcium – containing compounds to form calcium sulphate which has a low level of solubility. High sulphate concentration may have laxative effects on consumers if ingested. Chlorides re-enter the eco-system and may ultimately end up in the ground water. High salt content is only acceptable if the effluents are discharge into tidal/marine environments. The level of salt as of January 2019.

Conclusion

The results obtained from the study showed that the levels of temperature and turbidity are above the permissible limit of WHO while pH, Electrical Conductivity, heavy metals (with the exception of

chloride under acid Anionism can be determined by titration a known volume of effluent with a silver nitrate solution, using potassium chromate as an indicator. The presence of chloride on the other hand in the natural water could be attributed to pollution from sewage, minerals and industrial effluents (Mandel et al.; 2011) further non geochemical conditions could make chlorides to present in varying conditions (Aremu et al., 2011). Dietvorst (2013) carried out a water quality study in rural Cambodia which showed that a shallow aquifer was chemically less of a health risk than a deep aquifer; however, microbial contamination was considerable for both open and rope-pump shallow wells. The presence of iron and manganese may lead to the formation of incrustations of pipe mains by the deposition of ferric hydroxide and manganese oxide. Chloride concentration in excess of 250 mg/l may have an undesirable taste. Sulphate concentrations in excess of 250 mg/l may have a laxative effect on humans. Jameel et al., (2006) analysed groundwater samples from Pettavaithalai area of Tamilnadu and showed high values of cations and anions above the acceptable limits indicating groundwater contamination.

manganese during the dry season) and ions were found to be below the permissible limit of drinking water by WHO and the quality of groundwater in the study areas were not statistically significant difference between seasons. Hence, the water is suitable for consumption.

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